

**THE FORMATION OF PROPER KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS
THROUGH THE SUBJECT OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN
PREPARATION OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED SPECIALISTS IN THE NON-
PHILOLOGICAL UNIVERSITIES**

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Abstract

This article discusses the main problems and methods of the formation of proper knowledge through subject of a foreign language in preparation of highly qualified specialists in the non philological universities. The authors believe that the study of a foreign language in the preparation of specialists in various specialties is based on the lexical material of a particular area of professional activity. According to the authors, the formation of the personality of a specialist should be carried out in the process of studying any course and subject studied at the university. The existing problems of education require a comprehensive solution. This solution will be achieved using the program-target method.

Keywords: professional foreign language, competence-oriented education, professional English

Introduction

The formation of the personality of a specialist should be carried out in the process of studying any course and subject studied at the university. At present, it is not enough to confine ourselves to the narrow framework of professional training in one or another special subject. It is necessary to prepare ideologically convinced, highly qualified and erudite specialists who are skillfully versed not only in the intricacies of their profession, but also able to defend their opinion, their point of view on any issue relevant to everyday and scientific life. Currently, there is a tendency to expand ties in

various areas of scientific knowledge. This leads to the realization of the need to implement intercultural communicative and professional competence. And in this regard, a foreign language plays a special role. Currently, the main goal of teaching foreign languages is teaching it as a means of intercultural communication in the field of professional activity, as a means of shaping the personality of a future specialist, as one of the conditions for successful adaptation in the social and scientific space [1, c.11]. The study of a foreign language in a non-linguistic university is considered as an obligatory component of the professional training of a specialist with a higher education. The modern concept of language education in a non-linguistic university involves the creation of such a system of training a specialist that will allow him to easily adapt to dynamically changing conditions of professional activity, that is, aimed at professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages, dictated by the characteristics of the future profession or specialty. It involves a combination of mastering a professionally oriented foreign language with the development of personal qualities of students, knowledge of the culture of the country of the language being studied and the acquisition of special skills based on professional and linguistic knowledge. The role of a foreign language in the preparation of qualified specialists is very important. The last decade has seen a significant increase in the demand for mastery of foreign languages. Integration of higher education institutions in unified scientific and educational space, first of all, involves the formation of a class of such specialists who would be full-fledged members of the international scientific community

Methods and Literature Review

In modern conditions there are serious requirements for the level of training of a specialist in any industry (medicine, natural sciences, technical sciences, etc.). A very important and essential component of this training is the knowledge of a foreign language. The volume of professional information from various industries in the modern world is growing rapidly. The problem of access to knowledge sources can now be considered solved thanks to the widespread use of computer technologies.

However, the degree of awareness of a specialist is largely determined by one of his most important professional qualities - the ability to work with a text containing the necessary information, including text in a foreign language. The problem of interaction between a specialist and information, a specialist and a text is currently one of the most urgent, and knowledge of a foreign language is one of the conditions for solving this problem.

According to Aynutdinova (2011), the possibilities of a foreign language as a necessary part of the learning system are expanding, turning it into a means of education and comprehensive development of the individual; as a means of access to foreign-language information, due to the supranational nature of scientific knowledge, they have become the property of all mankind; as a means of intercultural communication in the context of professional activities of people. As an object of the methodology, Leontieva (2015) considers the process of learning a foreign language, that is, the educational process, which includes: the activities of teachers and students, the main forms of their interaction; programs, textbooks that provide training. In other words, the objects of the methodology, in her opinion, are real phenomena of the educational process in a material form. Beskorovaynaya (2011) noted that communicative competence is the ability to freely use language in communication, that is, to transmit and exchange thoughts in various situations in the process of interaction with other participants, correctly use the system of speech norms and choose a communicative behavior that is adequate to an authentic communication situation. Lyakhovitsky (1973) made a huge contribution to the development of the theory of professional oriented teaching of a foreign language. Parikova (1972) was engaged in the coordination of foreign language training with the training of core subjects. Preparation of a future specialist who is capable of continuous professional and personal self-development related not only to the development of his personal qualities, but also to his practical ability to perform his professional activities effectively on his own. That is why such concepts as independence, personal and professional self-

development, and professional self-realization are closely interrelated. This is quite well represented in the studies of local (Russian and Ukrainian) scientists. For example, the structure of the interaction between teacher and student were analyzed by Sergeev (2008).

Results

A foreign language as an academic subject is the basis for the formation of high knowledge and skills. The study of a foreign language in the preparation of specialists in various specialties is based on the lexical material of a particular area of professional activity. Sometimes a foreign language is compared with physical education, where no special mental effort is required to acquire the appropriate skills. However, such a comparison is hardly justified, since the development of thinking does not occur when performing physical exercises, while teaching foreign languages develops mental abilities, not to mention the fact that the content of the language material itself contributes to the development of thinking. And if you nevertheless make such a comparison, then it should be noted that a foreign language is a training of the mind, the development of thinking, without which it is impossible to educate an active, creative, thinking person. The formation of high knowledge and skills through the subject of a foreign language can be carried out in three areas: 1) work with language material, which is necessary to achieve the goal of learning - to be able to read and understand literature in the specialty, conduct a conversation on sociocultural and professional topics, 2) work with text material, 3) independent working of students during extracurricular time. Working with linguistic material offers the use of tasks and exercises that develop linguistic flair, linguistic guess. With the correct organization of work, it should lead not only to the formation of speech skills in a foreign language, but also to the development of thinking in the native language, a more accurate, clear command of the language of professional communication. It was shown that the formation of foreign language speech mechanisms is the basis for the development of

cognitive processes and functions of the psyche, and abstract logical and philological thinking are inextricably linked.

Discussion

When learning a foreign language, the integrative activity of the brain is activated. Speech is a tool of thinking and its development leads to the development of thinking. Thinking ensures the construction of a person's thought, that is, it encodes and recodes information, provides interaction with the outside world [2, p.92-93]. At the same time, all exercises must be creative in nature, be accessible in content for students to perform at the appropriate stage of learning. Work on them should be competitive in nature, and their implementation should bring moral satisfaction. The value of textual material used in the process of teaching foreign languages cannot be overestimated. With careful selection and organization, textual material can be used to form professional knowledge, ideological convictions, aesthetic and moral norms of behavior. The issue of selecting textual material was previously considered in a similar way [3, c.335-341]. It should only be noted that the textual material should correspond to the professional interests of students, be relevant, interesting in content, contain additional information on subjects studied at major departments. The text material selected for training must be authentic. It should be taken from original foreign-language sources and, if necessary, subjected to minimal adaptation. The development of skills for independent work of students is the key to the further use of the studied foreign language in their practical activities. Independent work should be purposeful, correspond to the level of knowledge of students, be approximately regulated in time. Unnecessarily difficult, time-consuming work can cause a negative attitude among students, discourage the desire to do it [4, p. 111-115]. Each of these areas has its own goals and objectives, and how they are solved, by what means the final result of learning is achieved, will depend on whether a foreign language will become one of the ways to gain professional knowledge, form a convinced, creatively thinking personality. Not a little important in shaping the personality of the future specialist is the personality of the teacher himself.

This applies to teachers of any subject and a foreign language in particular. A teacher of foreign languages in a non-linguistic university is different from a teacher of a foreign language in a language university. In addition to the fact that a teacher of foreign languages in a non-linguistic university must be a highly qualified specialist in his field of knowledge, that is, he must be proficient in all types of foreign language activities at a high professional level, he must be sufficiently competent in matters of the specialty in favor of which training is being conducted in a particular university. He must be familiar with the scientific style of presentation, which differs in universities of the natural sciences, technical and medical universities, know the terminology inherent in this profile of education. The primary task of a teacher of foreign languages in a non-linguistic university is to convince students of the need for knowledge of foreign languages in the modern world, to show that a foreign language will allow them to keep abreast of the main latest achievements in their chosen field of scientific knowledge, will bring their own discoveries to the attention of the world scientific community and achievements, conduct conversations and discussions on issues of interest to them with foreign friends and colleagues. A foreign language course in a non-linguistic university is professionally oriented. The essence of professionally-oriented teaching of a foreign language lies in its integration with major disciplines in order to obtain additional professional knowledge and form professionally significant personality traits. A modern specialist who has received a higher education should have a wide range of basic knowledge in his field of activity. A foreign language plays an important role in this process and acts as a means of increasing the professional competence and personal and professional development of students and is a necessary condition for the successful professional activity of a graduate of any university. At this stage in the development of society, the issue of raising education in our country to a higher, higher quality level has become acute. President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev speaks about this. He calls for the preparation of highly qualified specialists, not to chase the number of applicants in

order to increase funding for universities, but to accept applicants with good knowledge. The President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: “We need thinking young people, who, as a result, will join the ranks of high-class specialists. We need quality, not quantity. Without quality education, the country has no future.” Today, a high-class specialist is understood as a specialist who is competent in all types of foreign language activities. Expanding ties with foreign countries contributes to internationalization of scientific relations. For this reason, it is of particular importance to acquire a well-organized system of international information, functioning of which is impossible without specialists capable of independently extracting information from foreign sources, and use it in research. Due to the insufficient level of foreign language proficiency, our specialists spend energy and money on creating something that already exists in other countries. In this regard, it is a foreign language that plays the role of a means of achievement of professional realization of the personality. Modern world trends and professional requirements for specialists significantly increase the motivation of students to study foreign language. The modern employer prefers professionals who speak a foreign language as a means of foreign language professional communication, which involves establishing contacts, participation in meetings and negotiations, conducting business correspondence, etc. Strong recommendations of scientific supervisors of profiles specialties on the use of foreign experience in writing term papers, theses, as well as in the implementation of any other scientific activities quite effectively increase the motivation for learning foreign language. One of the main tasks of the foreign language teacher of the non-philological universities today is maintaining at the proper level the motivation of students to study a foreign language through the use of modern teaching aids, such as computer technologies, including training programs, testing, conferences, as well as traditional technologies with an update the content of teaching foreign languages. Selection of topics and issues foreign language communication is carried out taking into account real interests and needs of today's students. The current situation is such that increasing intensity of written

communication through the worldwide web, including the prompt movement of business correspondence is increased the need to master writing. Such an aspect as writing to the present moment was given relatively little time compared to other aspects of learning. Creating an international environment within the university is undoubtedly contributes to the emergence of students' motivation when studying a foreign language. The foreign language teachers are actively working to attract foreign teachers to give lectures and conduct practical classes. Classes are held both with students of non-linguistic specialties, and with first-year graduate students. Round tables held at the department together with a foreign language teacher, contribute to the improvement teacher qualifications.

Conclusion

The openness of modern Uzbek society, the expansion of business and cultural contacts of our country with the countries of the world community created a need for academic mobility, for specialists, speaking foreign languages in their professional activities. A foreign language is becoming an important resource of social and professional growth. Knowledge of a foreign language gives the future specialist access to foreign sources of information, without which at present the activity of a graduate specialist is unthinkable. Ability to work with original literature in the specialty includes obtaining information contained in the text, its critical reflection, generalization, analysis and assessment of reliability. Foreign language competence provides readiness of a university graduate to actually use the acquired knowledge in a professional environment. New requirements for university graduates are being imposed by an increasingly active participation of Russian enterprises and organizations in the international division labor. Expansion of professional international communication, business negotiations with foreign partners, work with technical documentation in a foreign language, the possibility of an internship abroad necessitate a fuller use of the possibilities foreign language in the professional training of future engineers and involve the formation of foreign language competence of

students, students in technical fields. As stated in state educational standards of higher professional education, a specialist in any field of activity should be able to "carry out foreign language communication in oral and written form" [1, p. 27], those. have a high level of readiness to communicate effectively with foreign partners in a foreign language. The future engineers know the achievements of science and technology, advanced domestic and foreign experience in the field of organization of production, labor and management. However, the decision similar tasks for the future engineer is impossible without the analysis of foreign publications and exchange of information in a foreign language. Due to this educational standards require taking into account professional specifics when learning a foreign language, its focus on the future professional activities of graduates.

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